

1 Taxonomic and metabolic profiling of glacial ice algal communities on 2 the Greenland Ice Sheet

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20

21 **Abstract**

22 During the summer melt season, glacier ice algal blooms are widespread in the area termed “dark
23 zone” in the southwest region of Greenland. Due to their pigmentation, glacier ice algae reduce the
24 albedo of the ice sheet, increasing surface melting. Despite their crucial role in the Greenland Ice Sheet
25 (GrIS) ecosystem, we know little about their metabolic potential or functions. Here, we present insights
26 into the links between microbial community composition using 18S and ITS2 sequencing and total
27 metabolic profiling of samples dominated by glacier ice algae from the GrIS. Our analysis of ITS2
28 secondary structures reveals that blooms are dominated by a single algal species, yet glacier ice algal
29 haplotype composition differs between sites (along a 40 km transect) and surface habitats (clean snow
30 vs. high algal biomass ice). Furthermore, metabolic composition changes during the development of

31 glacier ice algal blooms with an accumulation of fatty acids, although few differences were observed
32 between sites along the transect. In addition, a few metabolites showed diurnal variations and our data
33 suggest that under low light and freezing conditions, chlorophyll degradation, tocopherol abundance
34 and phytol remobilization may be the key compounds changing in the glacier ice algae dominated
35 samples. Overall, these results improve our understanding of the chemical environment in the GrIS
36 supraglacial microbial community structure and the contribution of the primary producers dominated
37 by the glacier ice algae. Our data also show that endo- and exo-metabolic patterns need to be
38 differentiated and that multiplexed data sets will help gain a better insight into these complex algae-
39 controlled ecosystems.

40

41 **1 Introduction**

42 The Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS) is a crucial component of Earth's water and climate system. It is one
43 of the largest supraglacial ecosystems on Earth after Antarctica. In contrast to snow-covered terminal
44 and alpine glaciers where snow algae play important roles (Hoham and Duval 2001; Takeuchi 2013;
45 Lutz et al. 2016; Anesio et al. 2017), primary production on the ice sheet is predominantly driven by
46 the glacier ice algal communities, which form extensive blooms during the summer melt season
47 (Yallop et al. 2012; Anesio et al. 2017; Stibal et al. 2017; Williamson et al. 2018; Lutz et al. 2018).
48 These communities comprises of very few specialized taxa belonging to the Zygnematales with their
49 key players being *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* and *Mesotaenium berggrenii* – recently renamed-
50 *Ancylonema alaskana* (Yallop et al. 2012; Lutz et al. 2018; Procházková et al. 2021). So far, taxonomic
51 studies have employed either microscopy (Yallop et al. 2012; Williamson et al. 2018) or sequencing
52 of 18S rRNA amplicons (Lutz et al. 2018; Rossel et al. 2025; Feord et al. 2025). Due to the varying
53 morphotypes in the algal life cycles as well as the low resolution of the 18S rRNA gene (Lutz et al.
54 2019), both approaches have their limitations in fully resolving the taxonomy of the glacier ice algae.
55 Thus, the exact number of glacier ice algal taxa on the GrIS remains unknown.

56 Bloom development begins with the onset of a melt season and is expressed in a brown-grey tinging
57 of the ice surface. The colouration is derived from the secondary metabolite purpurogallin carboxylic
58 acid-6-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside, which is produced by the algae to protect their photosynthetic
59 complexes from photoinhibition caused by excessive UV and visible light irradiation (Remias et al.
60 2012a, b). The pigmentation coupled with widespread algal distribution on the GrIS darkens the surface
61 of the glacier ice and significantly contributes to the reduction of surface albedo (Cook et al. 2017;

62 Stibal et al. 2017; Williamson et al. 2020; Halbach et al. 2022; Chevrollier et al. 2023), which is one
63 of the key factors in increasing glacial melt rates (Box et al. 2012). Little is known about the factors
64 controlling the algal abundance, their life cycle or functioning, and observations of spatial trends are
65 lacking (Yallop et al. 2012).

66 Algae are generally known to closely interact with other members of the microbial community (Hom
67 et al. 2015). For instance, metabolites exuded into the algal phycosphere (i.e., the microenvironment
68 surrounding an algal cell) can stimulate bacterial growth (Amin et al. 2012; Ramanan et al. 2016).
69 Similarly, both snow and glacier ice algal communities likely play important roles in the microbiome
70 of glaciers (Hoham and Duval 2001; Lutz et al. 2014, 2017) and ice sheets (Yallop et al. 2012; Stibal
71 et al. 2017; Williamson et al. 2018), including the glacier carbon and nutrient cycling. Furthermore,
72 these algal communities thrive irrespective of a multitude of environmental stress factors, including
73 high light irradiation, low temperatures, desiccation and nutrient limitation. Whilst these various
74 adaptations to extreme environmental conditions are worth investigating, and slowly draft genomes or
75 metagenome assembled genomes for various strains of terrestrial snow algae (Çiftçi et al. 2024; Hulatt
76 et al. 2024) and of bare ice inhabiting glacier ice algae (Bowles et al. 2024) are becoming available
77 the necessary reference genomes and transcriptomes – in particular for glacier ice algae are currently
78 lacking. In contrast, metabolites are conserved across organisms and can therefore be studied without
79 the availability of a genome sequence (Bundy et al. 2009). In addition, the metabolome represents the
80 ultimate response of an organism to its environment (Jamers et al. 2009) and is generally more long-
81 lived than the transcriptome. Despite these advantages, the number of studies using metabolomics to
82 expand the knowledge of cryophilic algal communities is very limited, and so far, only a few studies
83 have targeted the total metabolome of snow algae (Lutz et al. 2015; Davey et al. 2019) or cryoconite
84 cyanobacterial-dominated communities (Gokul et al. 2023). Recently, the exo-metabolome (Doting et
85 al. 2024) and endo-metabolome (Peter et al. 2024; Feord et al. 2025) of glacier ice algae-dominated
86 habitats have been studied; yet, studies on the total metabolome of glacier ice algae are also lacking.
87 To address this gap, we present data from an untargeted total metabolome profiling approach of glacier
88 ice algae-dominated samples from the Greenland ice sheet combined with comprehensive data sets on
89 community composition using a two-marker gene approach (18S and ITS2). Sampling occurred in the
90 southwestern ablation zone of the GrIS, along a 40 km transect perpendicular to the ice margin. This
91 allowed us to substitute time by space (i.e., samples were collected from sites that had experienced
92 varying extents of melting instead of sampling the same site over the whole melt period). We also
93 sampled similar sites over multiple years and added a day-night comparison for a glacier ice algae-

94 dominated site. We hypothesize that 1) the community and metabolic compositions shift during the
95 evolution of the glacial ice algal blooms, 2) the metabolic profile varies depending on the composition
96 of the glacial ice algal community structure, and 3) the metabolic profiles show a weak diurnal pattern.

97 **2 Material and Methods**

98 **2.1 Field sites and sampling**

99 Samples were collected on the GrIS between the 27th of July and the 5th of August 2016 and between
100 the 7th and 26th of June 2017 (**Fig. 1A**). The field locations were situated in the dark zone of the
101 southwestern margin of the Greenland Ice Sheet. In 2016, the field sites were spread across a 100 km
102 transect (**Fig. 1A**) (Lutz et al. 2018; McCutcheon et al. 2021) and consisted of sampling sites 1, 2, 3
103 and 4a, which had experienced varying extents of melting. Site 1, however, was too pristine in terms
104 of particulate loading and therefore was not included in this paper. In 2017, samples were collected
105 only at site 4b, which was in very close proximity to site 4a sampled in 2016 (**Fig. 1A, Table 1**).

106 A total of 16 samples comprising 11 high algal-dominated biomass ice ($H_{\text{bio_ice}}$) samples and two high
107 algal-dominated biomass snow ($H_{\text{bio_snow}}$) samples (with high biomass referring to a sample with
108 macroscopically visible high particle loads) and three clean snow (CS) samples (without
109 macroscopically visible particles) were collected. For DNA analyses, samples were collected into up
110 to five sterile 50 mL centrifuge tubes (for $H_{\text{bio_ice}}$ and $H_{\text{bio_snow}}$ samples) or into sterile ~ 1000 ml
111 sampling whirl pack bags (for CS samples). All samples were gently thawed at field-lab temperatures
112 (~5–10 °C) within a few hours post-sampling, and concentrated by gravimetric particle settling (for
113 $H_{\text{bio_ice}}$ and $H_{\text{bio_snow}}$) or filtered (for CS) through sterile Nalgene single-use filtration units (pore size
114 0.22 μm). The settled particles or the filters were transferred into 5 mL cryo-tubes and immediately
115 frozen in a cryo-shipper cooled to liquid nitrogen temperatures.

116 For total metabolomics profiling, duplicate samples of high and low algal-dominated biomass samples
117 were collected either in multiple 50 mL centrifuge tubes or 2x200 mL sterile whirl pack bags and
118 immediately mixed with equal volumes of a sterile methanol/water (v/v:50/50) solution in order to
119 quench the metabolites. In 2016, a few diurnal sample pairs were also collected, from within a ~ 1 m²
120 area of each other. Day samples were collected during the peak melting at 2 p.m. local time, when PAR
121 high-light was 1614 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at night, 2 a.m. local time, when the lowest temperature
122 and the lowest PAR light of <10 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ prevailed (**Table 1**). After fully thawing and
123 concentrating by gravimetric settling for up to 24 hours in the field-laboratory, for each sampling event

124 up to 5 replicate aliquots were transferred to 5 mL cryo-tubes and frozen. Both DNA and metabolite
125 tubes were stored and transported back to the home lab in a cryo-shipper cooled to liquid nitrogen
126 temperatures.

127

128 **2.2 DNA sequencing and bioinformatics**

129 DNA was extracted from all samples using the PowerSoil ($H_{\text{bio_ice}}$ and $H_{\text{bio_snow}}$) or PowerWater (clean
130 snow) DNA Isolation kits (MoBio Laboratories).

131 18S rDNA genes were amplified using the eukaryotic primers 528F (5'
132 GCGGTAATTCCAGCTCCAA) and 706R (5' AATCCRAGAATTTTCACCTCT) (Cheung et al. 2010)
133 spanning the V4–V5 hypervariable regions and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq in the University of
134 Bristol Genomics Facility using paired 300 bp reads. Sequence processing was performed in Qiime2
135 (v.2019.1). Quality filtering (**Supplementary Table 1**) was carried out using the dada2 pipeline
136 (parameters: --p-trunc-len-f=250, --p-trunc-len-r=200, --p-trim-feft-f=10, --p-trim-left-r=10). The
137 amplicon sequence variants (ASV) in the filtered libraries were classified using classify-sklearn and
138 the Silva database (silva-132-99-nb-classifier) (Quast et al. 2012). Sequences matching chloroplast and
139 mitochondrial DNA were excluded from the data set. The resulting feature table was rarefied to the
140 lowest sample size (i.e., 59000) and additionally only ASVs with a minimum frequency count of 10
141 were retained. Final taxonomic assignments were made manually based on NCBI BLAST scores.

142 ITS2 rDNA was amplified using the primers 5.8SbF2 and LSULP (“ITS2ice”) optimized for
143 Zygnematophyceae (Remias et al. 2023) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq at the Department of
144 Environmental Science at Aarhus University using 2 x 250 bp reads. Sequence processing was
145 performed in Qiime2 (v.2020.8). Quality filtering (**Supplementary Table 2**) was carried out using the
146 dada2 pipeline. ITS2 regions of forward and reverse reads were extracted separately using itsxpress
147 (“trim-pair-output-unmerged”) and subsequently filtered, trimmed and denoised into ASVs using
148 dada2. Reads were not further trimmed. The resulting feature table was rarefied to the lowest sample
149 size (i.e., 10900), and taxonomic assignments were made manually based on NCBI BLAST scores.
150 The ITS2 rRNA secondary structures and subsequent species delimitation based on the detection of
151 CBCs have been published in Remias et al. 2023.

152 Bar charts were created using the R package “ggplot2”. Pairwise comparisons between the three
153 sample groups (i.e., CS vs H_{bio_ice}, sites 2/3 vs 4a, 2 am vs 2 pm) were calculated in R (function =
154 “pairwise.t.test”, p.adjust = “BH”, pooled standard deviation to account for unequal variance) for the
155 dominant ASVs corresponding to eukaryotic divisions (e.g., Chlorophyta, Charophyta, Fungi), algal
156 species and glacial ice algal haplotypes.

157 Raw sequence reads were submitted to the SRA and are available under accession number
158 PRJNA564214.

159

160 **2.3 Total metabolite extractions and analyses**

161 Two to three replicates per metabolite sample were slowly thawed on ice, transferred from the 5 mL
162 cryo-tube to 15 mL centrifuge tubes and re-frozen at -80°C in a horizontal position to be lyophilized
163 for 24 hours. Metabolites were extracted from the lyophilized material using a biphasic extraction
164 method. First, a pre-cooled (4°C) extraction mix containing methanol/chloroform/water at ratios of
165 23.5/10/2.5/1 was prepared with the sorbitol prepared from a stock solution with a concentration of
166 0.2mg/mL in methanol. This mix was added to each sample tube and tubes were vortexed three times
167 and then incubated on a shaker for 1 h at 28°C with the tubes vortexed every 10 min. Particles were
168 sedimented by gravimetric settling for 30 min. The liquid supernatant was transferred to 2 mL
169 Eppendorf tubes and combined with 400 µL of MilliQ water. The tubes were centrifuged at 14,000
170 rpm (20800 g) for 5 min in order to separate the layers. Two aliquots (500 and 200 µL) of the upper
171 polar layer were transferred into separate 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and dried down in a rotary vacuum
172 concentrator at room temperature overnight. In a second extraction step, 1 mL of cold extraction mix
173 without Sorbitol (Methanol/Chloroform/Water:23.5/10/2.5) was added to the remaining sample
174 material in the 15 mL centrifuge tubes and re-combined with the residues of the previous extraction
175 step (lower lipophilic phase). The samples were incubated on a shaker overnight and particles were
176 sedimented by gravimetric settling for 30 min. The liquid supernatant was transferred to 2 mL
177 centrifuge tubes and mixed with 400 µL of water. The tubes were centrifuged at 14,000 rpm (20800 g)
178 for 5 min in order to separate the layers. Two aliquots (600 and 200 µL) of the upper polar layer were
179 transferred to the dried down samples of the previous extraction step (500+600 and 200+200). An
180 aliquot of 150 µL of the lower lipophilic phase was transferred to new 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes. All
181 aliquots were dried down in a rotary vacuum concentrator overnight at room temperature.

182 Gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) data acquisition was performed as described in
183 detail by Dethloff et al. (2014). For data mining and annotation of the acquired chromatogram, pre-
184 processing was performed as described in Dethloff et al. (2014), using TagFinder (Luedemann et al.
185 2011) for data-matrix generation. Signals were annotated through manual supervision using the Golm
186 Metabolome Database repository of mass spectra, considering their retention indices (Kopka et al.
187 2005; Hummel et al. 2007, 2010). The 'best quantitative information' metabolite hits from the raw
188 intensity metabolite data matrix were considered for further analysis (**Supplementary Data file**). The
189 metabolite matrix was filtered to remove contaminants and internal standards. The raw intensities of
190 the samples were background-subtracted from the blank and processed in the online web tool
191 Metaboanalyst 5.0 (<https://www.metaboanalyst.ca/home.xhtml>) (Pang et al. 2021, 2022). For statistical
192 calculations, data were normalized with parameters available in Metaboanalyst 5.0 by sample
193 normalization by sum, no data transformation and data scaling (mean centred and divided by the
194 standard deviation of each variable). Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) was used
195 to understand the differences in metabolomic profiles between sample types (CS and H_{bio_ice}), time
196 (day and night) and sites (2, 3 and 4a). Different R packages like ggplot2, ggpubr, omu, etc. were used
197 for all plot generation and statistical analysis (Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis tests).

198

199 **3 Results**

200 **3.1 Community composition**

201 We have assessed the eukaryotic community composition from 16 sites comprising 11 high algal
202 biomass ice (H_{bio_ice}), two high algal biomass snow (H_{bio_snow}) (macroscopically visible particles) and
203 three clean snow (CS) samples, which were collected across a 40 km (sites 2, 3, 4a, 4b) transect during
204 the melt seasons of 2016 and 2017 (**Fig. 1A, Table 1**). Based on light microscopy, the algal
205 communities were dominated by two morphotypes – smaller single cells and filamentous chains (**Fig.**
206 **1B**).

207 Chloroplastida (mostly Charophyta) and fungi were the two dominant eukaryotic taxonomic groups
208 with the highest sequence abundance in the 18S rRNA data set (**Fig. 1C, Supplementary Table 3**).
209 Charophyta showed the highest relative abundance across the majority of samples. The only exception
210 was the clean snow samples, which were characterized by a significantly ($p=0.015$) higher relative
211 abundance of sequences assigned to Fungi and a lower abundance of Charophyta ($p=0.003$) (**Fig. 1C,**

212 **Table 2, Supplementary Table 3**). There were no significant differences in the relative abundances
213 of Charophyta, Chlorophyta and Fungi between sites 2/3 and 4a or between diurnal samples.

214 The algal 18S rRNA sequences were dominated by two ASVs matching *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii*
215 (100% and 99.7% similarities with the reference sequence) across all samples. The two *A.*
216 *nordenskiöldii* haplotypes exhibited a clear geographic distinction. Haplotype 2 was more abundant in
217 samples from sites 2 and 3 ($p < 0.001$), whereas haplotype 1 dominated the algal community in samples
218 from site 4a ($p < 0.001$; **Fig.1, Table 2, Supplementary Table 4**). Haplotype 1 was also more abundant
219 in clean snow samples from 4b ($p < 0.001$), whereas haplotype 2 was more abundant in H_{bio_ice} samples
220 from site 4b ($p < 0.001$; **Table 2**). Low abundance algal taxa included *Raphidonema/Koliella* spp.,
221 *Sanguina nivaloides* (in H_{bio_snow}), *Chlainomonas* sp. and *Trebouxia* spp. Surprisingly, no sequences
222 matched *Ancylonema alaskana*.

223 The sequencing of the ITS2 marker using Zygnematophyceae-specific primers (Remias et al. 2023)
224 resulted in a total number of 18 representative ASVs. Four abundant and eight rare ASVs matched
225 *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* (95.83-100% similarities with the reference sequence; **Fig. 1E,**
226 **Supplementary Table 5**). However, the analysis of the ITS2 secondary structures classified them all
227 as one single species. Most haplotypes, and in particular the high abundance ones, significantly varied
228 in their relative abundance between sites (sites 2/3 vs 4a) and habitats (CS vs H_{bio_ice}, **Table 2**). Sites 2
229 and 3 were dominated by *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* haplotype 1, whereas sites 4a and 4b were overall
230 more diverse, with CS and H_{bio_ice} samples showing different abundance profiles. Similar to the 18S
231 data set, sequences matching *Ancylonema alaskana* and *Raphidonema nivale* were very low-abundant
232 ($< 0.2\%$, **Supplementary Table 5**). The remaining four rare ASVs did not result in any blast hits.

233

234 **3.2 Metabolome profiling**

235 A total of 9704 metabolite features were detected from the GC-MS data, among which 114 metabolite
236 compounds were identified. Most of the metabolite hits were unknown (23%) or could not be assigned
237 to a known metabolite in the database (22%), and the other known metabolites belong mainly to fatty
238 acids and lipids (16%). Fatty acids, alcohols and alkanes were more abundant in all samples (apparent
239 composition), whereas sugars were less abundant. We could not annotate many compounds in our
240 study, because the targeting of non-model organisms, which dominate the biomas in our samples, are
241 severely underrepresented in databases. We also know little about the (bio)chemical fate of metabolites

242 released from the algal-dominated biomass into the environment and how this is affected by the
243 combination of biotic and abiotic chemical conversion reactions during metabolite extraction.

244 The Partial Least-Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) multivariate pattern recognition models
245 showed that there was a difference in the patterns of samples where they clustered between the different
246 sample groups. The PLS-DA score plot of the CS and H_{bio_ice} sample types separated with the first
247 (23.1%) and second (20.7%) components (**Fig. 2A**). PLS-DA separated the samples between the three
248 sampling sites (2, 3 and 4a) into different groups with 14.3% (component 1) and 33.3% (component 2)
249 (**Fig. 2B**). Samples collected at different times and light conditions (high-light vs. low-light; Table 1),
250 also clustered independently based on PLS-DA component 1 (24%) and component 2 (28%) (**Fig. 2C**).
251 This observation suggests that there are differences in the overall metabolomic profile between the
252 groups of replicate samples based on the score plots of the first two components in the PLS-DA
253 multivariate analysis.

254 Metabolites belonging to specific classes such as lipids, fatty acids and sterols were present and non-
255 parametric statistical tests (Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis test) were used to assess which metabolites
256 distinguish the sample groups. To determine if the metabolic compositions shift during the
257 development of glacier ice algal blooms, we compared low (CS, higher fungal abundance, **Fig. 1C**)
258 and high glacier ice algal (H_{bio_ice}) biomass samples (**Fig. 1D**). The metabolite intensities between CS
259 and H_{bio_ice} revealed no significant differences (**Fig. 3**) yet some metabolites showed slight (but not
260 significant) variations between these groups. The metabolites that indicate a tendency for a change
261 include dodecanoic acid, heptadecanoic acid and nonanoic acid.

262 Further, we also compared the differences in these metabolic compounds (lipids, fatty acids and sterols)
263 in samples from different sampling sites along the 40 km transect, in particular because these samples
264 showed differences in algal haplotypes (**Fig. 1**). Samples from site 4a had a higher abundance of *A.*
265 *nordenskiöldii* haplotype 1 and samples from sites 2 and 3 had a higher abundance of *A. nordenskiöldii*
266 haplotype 2. In terms of total metabolites, no significant differences in metabolite intensities were
267 observed between sampling sites (**Fig. 4**), yet some metabolites showed variation in their pattern
268 between sites. These includes a higher abundance of the fatty acids heptadecanoic acid, 9,12-
269 octadecadienoic acid, nonanoic acid and 9-octadecenoic acid in site 2, compared to sites 3 and 4a.
270 Finally, we compared samples collected during the highest (2 p.m.; 1614 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and
271 lowest (2 a.m.; 0 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) light conditions to evaluate if any diurnal variations are present
272 (**Fig. 5**), and again, total metabolite intensities did not vary significantly with light conditions, but some

273 compounds showed differences at high vs. low light. For example, dodecanoic acid, eicosanoic acid,
274 heptadecanoic acid, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and octadecenoic acid showed an increase at high light,
275 while 9,12-octadecadienoic acid, 6,9,12-octadecatrienoic acid, 9-octadecenoic acid, tocopherol, phytol
276 and nonanoic acid showed a higher intensity at low light.

277 .

278

279 **4 Discussion**

280 We have documented above that the algal community changes during the development of glacier ice
281 algal blooms in the southwestern part of the Greenland Ice Sheet, but this change is only at the
282 haplotype level and not at the species level. Furthermore, we document the overall total metabolic
283 composition of the microbial community that is dominated by glacier ice algae, with minor distinct
284 metabolic differences across sites, but few metabolite variations as a function of light exposure.

285 So far, studies of GrIS microbiomes using microscopy (Yallop et al. 2012; Stibal et al. 2017;
286 Williamson et al. 2018) or 18S rRNA sequencing (Lutz et al. 2018) have consistently described
287 *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* and *Ancylonema alaskana* as the two dominant species of glacier ice algae
288 throughout the ablation period. However, the analysis of the ITS2 secondary structures revealed that
289 blooms are dominated by a single glacial ice algal species matching the reference sequence of
290 *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* (Remias et al. 2023) (**Fig. 1**). Primer biases can be ruled out since 18S as
291 well as ITS2 sequences of *Ancylonema alaskana* have been successfully amplified elsewhere (Remias
292 et al. 2023) using the same primers as in this study. Unfortunately, amplicon studies are limited in their
293 read lengths. Thus, it is impossible to match corresponding 18S and ITS2 haplotypes and state whether
294 the haplotype diversity can be found within one individual (i.e., multiple copies of rRNA operons
295 within one genome) or whether it can be attributed to different populations. However, differences
296 between haplotype abundances between sites and habitats suggest that the diversity is more likely
297 derived from different individuals that are subjected to competition and selection. All haplotypes are
298 present across the 40 km transect; only their relative abundances vary. This suggests that these algae
299 are not limited in their dispersal on a regional scale. However, only a comprehensive metagenome-
300 assembled genomics approach would resolve true diversity (Jaarsma et al. 2023).

301 Further, we found mildly significant ($p < 0.1$) differences in the metabolome profiles between CS and
302 $H_{\text{bio_ice}}$ samples (**Fig. 3**). Fatty acids such as dodecanoic acid and 9-Octadecenoic acid (oleic acid) were

303 slightly higher in H_{bio_ice} samples. This could be due to a higher algal biomass and/or accumulation in
304 algal cells during bloom development. For example, 9-octadecenoic acid is an unsaturated fatty acid,
305 which is one of the most abundant fatty acids in nature and has also been found in the polar marine
306 algae species *H. grandifolius* and *K. antarctica*, including (Ko et al. 2022).

307 The metabolic profiles from the three different sampling sites (2, 3 and 4a) showed some differences
308 (**Fig. 4**), which could be due to the different duration of melting experienced (longest in 4a) and/or
309 differences in the haplotype composition of the glacier ice algal community. Individual metabolites
310 were not significantly different between the sampling sites, yet we could observe some trends. Samples
311 collected at high-light (2 p.m.) vs. low-light (2 a.m.) showed no major differences in their metabolic
312 profiles (**Fig. 5**). The fatty acids heptadecanoic acid, 9,12-octadecadienoic acid, nonanoic acid and 9-
313 octadecenoic acid showed similar patterns with the highest abundance in site 2, followed by sites 3 and
314 4a. These fatty acids were also found in the high-light and low-light samples. Fatty acids are one of
315 the primary metabolites with many functional roles in microalgae. They are a major component of cell
316 membrane phospholipids to maintain membrane fluidity and are physiological regulators during stress
317 conditions (Lu et al. 2012). Psychrophilic microeukaryotes can regulate the ratio of saturated to
318 unsaturated fatty acids in the cell depending on the ambient temperature. A higher proportion of
319 unsaturated fatty acids in the cell allows it to withstand cold and freezing conditions, thereby
320 maintaining the fluidity of its cell membrane, and vice versa.

321 Tocopherol was more abundant in site 4a, where melting had occurred earlier and with a different
322 haplotype composition of *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* (**Fig. 1E**). Tocopherols or Vitamin E are
323 generally synthesized by photosynthetic organisms. Alpha (α)-tocopherol, which plays a major role in
324 the cell by protecting the cell membranes from oxidative damage due to photons as an antioxidant
325 compound. Many species of microalgae produce α -Tocopherol, like *Euglena gracilis* from freshwater
326 and *Dunaliella tertiolecta* and *Tetraselmis suecica* from the marine environment (Carballo-Cárdenas
327 et al. 2003). In glacier habitats, due to high light stress, glacier ice algae may produce tocopherol-like
328 compounds to maintain their cell membrane integrity. α -tocopherol is known for its vitamin E
329 antioxidant activity and is presumed to protect chloroplast lipids and chlorophylls against photo-
330 oxidative damage (Li et al. 2012). It is also synthesized by several snow and permafrost algae from
331 polar regions in response to high light conditions and low nitrogen levels (Leya et al. 2009).

332 The diurnal sample pairs showed variations in their metabolic profiles (**Fig. 5**), yet these were not
333 statistically relevant. The observed differences likely reflect the stress that the algae-dominated

334 samples experience due to variations in day-night light intensity, temperature (melting *vs.* freezing),
335 and oxidative stress. Among the metabolites of interest, the abundance of saturated fatty acids (e.g.,
336 dodecanoic acid, heptadecanoic acid, and hexacosanoic acid) is lower during the night, while the
337 unsaturated fatty acids (e.g., 9,12-octadecadienoic acid, 6,9,12-octadecatrienoic acid, and 9-
338 octadecenoic acid) are higher during the night. Fatty acids are primary metabolites with many
339 functional roles in microalgae. They are a major component of cell membrane phospholipids to
340 maintain membrane fluidity and are physiological regulators during stress conditions (Lu et al. 2012).
341 Psychrophilic microeukaryotes can regulate the ratio of saturated to unsaturated fatty acids in the cell
342 depending on the ambient temperature. A higher proportion of unsaturated fatty acids in the cell allows
343 it to withstand cold and freezing conditions, thereby maintaining the fluidity of its cell membrane, and
344 vice versa. This mechanism may occur in the glacier ice algae dominated samples during the diurnal
345 day and night cycles, as a response to the low-temperature conditions. Moreover, heptadecanoic acid
346 varies between both sample types (CS and H_{bio_ice}) and also between day and night samples. Perhaps
347 this is also one of the main fatty acids that may play a functional role in the algae for their survival on
348 the glacier.

349 Furthermore, both phytol and tocopherol intensity increased during the night. Phytol is involved in
350 many pathways; for instance, it is a constituent of chlorophyll, one of the most abundant isoprenoids
351 in the biosphere, and an important precursor for tocopherol (vitamin E) synthesis (Hörtensteiner 1999;
352 Hofius and Sonnewald 2003; Rontani and Volkman 2003). The remobilization of phytol by chlorophyll
353 degradation is essential for growth and development in higher plants (Dorp et al. 2015). In addition, it
354 has been shown that chlorophyll hydrolysis induces tocopherol and fatty acid phytyl (phytol derivative)
355 synthesis. This pathway seems to play an important role in particularly under stress and senescence
356 conditions (Kanwischer 2007), and may be this could be an essential process for glacier ice algal
357 communities occurring during low light conditions.

358 Overall, the number of metabolites identified in the present study as exhibiting a diurnal signal appears
359 to be considerably low. For instance, 18% of the metabolites in *Ostreococcus tauri* were affected by
360 diurnal changes (Hirth et al. 2017). Doting et al. 2024 also compared the exo-metabolite profile of
361 microbial communities from the Greenland ice sheet and found significant differences between midday
362 and midnight samples, suggesting that the metabolism of glacier ice algae on the ice sheet changes due
363 to light conditions.

364 The very low number of metabolites identified in our present study may be due to the lack of an
365 available metabolite database for the glacier ice algae. Further, it was difficult to observe any difference
366 between the sample types because there is no ideal protocol for preserving metabolites in
367 environmental ice and snow samples in a remote location, since a large volume of ice/snow has to be
368 melted and biomass has to be concentrated before the samples can be stored at liquid nitrogen
369 conditions. The mixing of the ice and snow samples with a diluted methanol/water solution just after
370 collection was, to our knowledge, the only way to immediately quench the metabolites. Conversely,
371 some cells may have lysed during this process, and free metabolites may have been lost during the
372 concentration process. Recently, Peter et al. 2024 demonstrated the importance of ice sample
373 processing from the field to the laboratory with their study of the endo-metabolite profile of glacier ice
374 algal communities on the Greenland Ice Sheet. The untargeted metabolomics approach showed that
375 melting the ice samples at different temperatures could affect the metabolite profile and that rapid
376 melting could potentially reduce the variation in endo-metabolite composition.

377 Furthermore, the storage of the metabolites in methanol may have induced the esterification of fatty
378 acids, resulting in fatty acid methyl esters. Thus, it cannot be ruled out that the latter ones might be
379 artefacts. However, there is evidence for the biosynthesis of fatty acid methyl esters in the green algae
380 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Herrera-Valencia et al. 2012). Second, the two light conditions, despite
381 being the two daily extremes during the melt season, might not have been sufficiently different in order
382 to evoke diurnal patterns. Although *Ancylonema nordenskiöldii* is well adapted to high light conditions
383 (Remias et al. 2012a) and can tolerate irradiance up to 4,000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (Williamson et al.
384 2020), the irradiance intensity at 2 p.m. during the melt season ($\sim 1,700 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) can be
385 sufficient to suppress the algal photochemistry (Williamson et al. 2020). Similarly, photochemistry is
386 likely suppressed at 2 a.m. due to the absence of photosynthetic active radiation (PAR = 0, **Table 1**).
387 Third, it may be the case that in general, these algae have only a small metabolic pool size with diurnal
388 fluctuations. Here, we did not artificially manipulate the light conditions since the aim was to study the
389 natural physiological response of these algae to their environment. However, a more time-resolved
390 sampling is needed in the future.

391 A relatively high number of metabolites could not be identified, which may be because the metabolome
392 of these algae has not been studied before and contains unique (and thus potentially interesting
393 metabolites), which are not produced by other (green) algae. It was striking that the relative abundance
394 of phenolic compounds was overall very low. In particular, since the phenol-like pigment purpurogallin

395 is one of the main compounds in glacial ice algal cells (Remias et al. 2012b, a) and can be ~11 times
396 the content of chlorophyll *a* (Williamson et al. 2020). It might be in the pool of unknown metabolites,
397 which should be targeted in future studies.

398 Here, we cannot fully rule out the bacterial and fungal contributions to the pool of metabolites.
399 However, we previously showed that the bacterial and fungal community composition showed a
400 significantly higher similarity within one site than within one habitat (McCutcheon et al. 2021). Thus,
401 only the metabolic comparison of sites 2/3 and 4a would be affected by differences in the bacterial
402 community composition. In addition, it has been shown that algal net primary production was at least
403 28 and up to 404 times higher than bacterial production in samples from the same area (Nicholes et al.
404 2019). Therefore, the bacterial metabolic contribution to the overall metabolome is likely of negligible
405 importance.

406 Here, we provide insights into the metabolomic processes of dominated glacier ice algae communities
407 on the Greenland Ice Sheet co-occurring with other microbes by studying their total metabolome
408 profile. This can be used as a basis for future targeted and non-targeted metabolomics studies. Overall,
409 such studies will contribute to a better understanding of these communities and their functioning in the
410 Greenland ice sheet ecosystem.

411

412 **Conflict of Interest**

413 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
414 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

415

416 **Author Contributions**

417 SL and LGB designed the study and collected the samples in Greenland; SL extracted the DNA and
418 metabolites and did the bioinformatics on the amplicons; together with AE and JK, they quantified
419 and analysed the metabolomic data sets; SL and AM did the statistical evaluation of the metabolite
420 data sets; SL wrote the first draft of the paper with input from all co-authors.

421

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435

436

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609 **Data Availability Statement**

610 The datasets generated for this study can be found in the SRA under accession number PRJNA564214.

611 All other data are available in the supplementary information.

612

613 **Figures**

614

615 **Figure 1:** A) Map showing the sampling sites in southwest Greenland in 2016 (sites 2, 3, 4a) and 2017
 616 (4b; Image source: Google Earth 18.01.2019). B) Representative light micrographs of the two most
 617 abundant glacier ice algal morphotypes. C) The eukaryotic (18S), D) algal (18S) and E) glacier ice
 618 algal (ITS2) community compositions of the most abundant taxa. Full details can be found in
 619 Supplementary Tables 2-4.

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623 **Figure 2:** Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) score plots showing samples
624 clustered separately as various groups between the (A) Habitats [Clean snow (CS) and High algal
625 biomass ice (H_{bio_ice})], (B) Sites (2, 3 and 4a) and (C) Time [high-light (2 p.m.) and low-light (2 a.m.)].

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629 **Figure 3:** Box plot of normalized intensity for the metabolites showing the differences between the
 630 habitats [Clean snow (CS) and High algal biomass ice (Hbio_ice)]. The Y-axis represents the
 631 normalized intensity of metabolites. The negative value in the Y-axis is due to normalization and
 632 scaling from the Metaboanalyst program. Wilcoxon non-parametric test was used to analyze the
 633 significant difference in the intensity of the metabolites.

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636 **Figure 4:** Box plot of normalized intensity for the metabolites showing the differences between the
637 sites (2, 3 and 4a). The Y-axis represents the normalized intensity of metabolites. The negative value
638 in the Y-axis is due to normalization and scaling from the Metaboanalyst program. The Kruskal-Wallis
639 non-parametric test was used to analyze the significant difference in the intensity of the metabolites.

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643 **Figure 5:** Box plot of normalized intensity for the metabolites showing the differences between the
 644 time [day high-light (2 p.m.) and night low-light (2 a.m.)]. The Y-axis represents the normalized
 645 intensity of metabolites. The negative value in the Y-axis is due to normalization and scaling from the
 646 Metaboanalyst program. Wilcoxon non-parametric test was used to analyze the significant difference
 647 in the intensity of the metabolites.

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651 **Tables**

652 **Table 1:** Overview of all snow and ice samples collected in 2016 and 2017 for DNA sequencing and
 653 metabolomics analyses.

Sample ID	Sample type	Site	Date of collection	GPS location	Elevation [m]	PAR [$\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]
GrIS16_2	H _{bio_ice}	2	27.07.2016	N 67°05.717' W 48°30.648'	1385	
GrIS16_3	H _{bio_ice}	3	27.07.2016	N 67°05.392' W 48°53.708'	1238	
GrIS16_4	H _{bio_snow}	3	27.07.2016	N 67°05.477' W 48°53.573'	1236	
GrIS16_5	H _{bio_ice}	4a	31.07.2016, 2 p.m.	N 67°04.462' W 49°21.254'	1015	1614
GrIS16_6	H _{bio_ice}	4a	31.07.2016, 2 p.m.	N 67°04.470' W 49°21.285'	1013	1614
GrIS16_7	H _{bio_ice}	4a	01.08.2016, 2 a.m.	N 67°04.462' W 49°21.254'	1015	0
GrIS16_8	H _{bio_ice}	4a	01.08.2016, 2 a.m.	N 67°04.470' W 49°21.285'	1013	0
GrIS16_9	H _{bio_ice}	2	05.08.2016	N 67°05.389' W 48°30.657'	1402	
GrIS16_10	H _{bio_ice}	3	05.08.2016	N 67°05.487' W 48°53.984'	1236	
GrIS16_11	H _{bio_snow}	3	05.08.2016	N 67°05.524' W 48°53'863'	1237	
GrIS17_18	CS	4b	07.06.2017	N 67°04.673' W 49°20.614'	1039	
GrIS17_19	CS	4b	08.06.2017	N 67°04.693' W 49°20.598'	1040	
GrIS17_20	CS	4b	10.06.2017	N 67°04.693' W 49°20.600'	1042	
GrIS17_26	H _{bio_ice}	4b	25.06.2017, 2p.m.	N 67°04.584' W 49°20.607'	1034	
GrIS17_28	H _{bio_ice}	4b	27.06.2017, 2p.m.	N 67°04.584' W 49°20.607'	1034	
GrIS17_35	H _{bio_ice}	4b	26.06.2017, 2a.m.	N 67°04.584' W 49°20.607'	1034	

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656 **Table 2:** Pairwise comparisons between sample groups and the ASVs corresponding to eukaryotic
 657 divisions, algal species and glacial ice algal haplotypes. Significant p-values (<0.05) are highlighted in
 658 bold.

Sample groups	CS vs H _{bio_ice}	sites 2/3 vs 4a	2 a.m.vs 2 p.m.
ASVs			
Eukaryotes			
Charophyta	0.003	0.49	0.72
Chlorophyta	0.71	0.47	0.18
Fungi	0.015	0.28	0.92
Metazoa	0.42	0.003	0.84
Ciliophora	1	0.24	0.16
Dinoflagellata	0.23	0.86	0.72
Cercozoa	0.85	0.014	0.43
Algae			
<i>Ancylonema nordenskiöldii</i> haplotype 1	0.006	<0.001	0.31
<i>Ancylonema nordenskiöldii</i> haplotype 2	0.004	<0.001	0.29
Trebouxiophyceae sp.	0.33	0.42	0.77
<i>Chlainomonas</i> sp.	0.61	0.005	0.19
<i>Sanguina nivaloides</i>	0.65	0.27	0.44
Prasiolales sp.	0.19	0.9	0.96
<i>Trebouxia jamesii</i>	0.19	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Raphidonema/Koliella</i> spp.	0.25	0.79	1
A. nordenskiöldii haplotypes			
Haplotype 1	0.037	0.027	0.79
Haplotype 2	0.045	0.04	0.94
Haplotype 3	0.026	<0.001	0.99
Haplotype 4	0.091	0.015	0.64
Haplotype 5	0.035	0.043	-
Haplotype 6	0.33	0.17	0.5
Haplotype 7	0.25	0.04	-
Haplotype 8	0.15	-	-

